

Practical fast and non-intrusive ONU Activation procedure in Coherent udWDM-PON

Victor Polo, Santiago Tabares, Xavier Canals, Josep Segarra and Josep Prat, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—The development of coherent high density WDM PONs, forecasted as one of the promising technologies to increase the spectral efficiency and reduce the energy consumption, can be obstructed by the limited tunability, high wavelength drifts and tuning transients of the DFB lasers used in PONs. In this work, a new non-intrusive, colorless and scalable channel allocation procedure is experimentally validated using simple EML lasers as transmitters and local oscillators.

Index Terms—Access PON, activation, allocation, coherent PON, EML, thermal tuning, TO-Can, udWDM

I. INTRODUCTION

COHERENT Passive Optical Networks (PONs) are being considered as a feasible advanced candidate for future edge networks due to their increased capacity, power budget, spectral efficiency in optical and electrical domains and no latency. Over the widely deployed splitter-based PONs, time division multiplexing (TDM) is used as the best choice due to its simplicity and coexistence with legacy networks. The forecasted services to be provided through next-generation networks require increased capacity and granularity, as well as reduced latency to support the incoming technologies such as new access networks, 6G fronthaul, industrial networks, business solutions and edge cloud. For example, 50G PON strongly depends on a high-power transmitter and complex equalization at the receiver [1]. Research suggests that 25G/50G PON might be the last generation of feasible TDM PON without optical amplification [2]. For this reason, the increase of capacity via multiple wavelengths is a striking proposal. The wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) provides point-to-point connections over a physical point-to-multipoint network topology [3], being an attractive solution for Fiber-to-the-home (FTTH) and enabling the concept of Fiber-to-the-user (FTTU/FTTx). Coherent WDM systems enable to reuse the passive-splitter Optical Distribution Network (ODN) typically by using multi-electrode widely-tunable lasers, which encompass critical operation and high cost; to meet the cost restrictions in access, a number of smart techniques have been proposed, towards the ‘lite’ coherent transceiver [4-8].

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As mentioned in [3], a key enabler is a wavelength agnostic optical transceiver at the Optical Network Unit (ONU) side. This can be done using the same Distributed Feed-Back (DFB) lasers as in conventional PONs, with random wavelength and fine thermal tuning. With the proper control methodology, it can provide colourlessness in an ultra-dense-WDM (udWDM) scenario at minimum cost. The statistical analysis performed in [9] exposed a spectral channel efficiency of 90% for a 256 ONUs PON (allocated in 310 slots), with the proposed algorithms, for setting-up and reconfiguring the ONUs, in variable environmental conditions. These algorithms, managed by the Optical Line Terminal (OLT), make use of basic physical-layer equalization functions to control the ONU and OLT lasers, specifically their wavelength tuning range and power. In [10] the general methodology was proposed and the procedure steps were carried out separately in a narrow band, but it did not consider practical aspects of thermal transients, wide wavelength drift with the bias current and scalability.

In this work, a practical methodology for the bidirectional spectral PON allocation is implemented following the required procedure design of simple colourless coherent transceivers with cooled Electro-Absorption Modulated Laser (EML) in low cost TO-Can package, and proof-of-concept demonstrated for the first time to our knowledge.

II. PHYSICAL RESTRICTIONS AND SPECTRAL PLAN

The fact that PON networks use a single fiber bidirectionally and non-preselected simple DFB lasers makes them susceptible to reflective noise and crosstalk, especially if the coherent transceivers use the same fiber band for down and up-stream.

The channel spacing is as narrow as 6.25 GHz, transmitting up to 10 Gbps [8]. The DFB package TEC can tune the laser continuously beyond 375 GHz with limited consumption, so being able to tune 64 channels without crosstalk; in contemporary laser packages the thermal response might take several seconds to stabilize and there exists a deviation of tenths of GHz when the injection current is changed (e.g. when powering up). The strong mixed dynamic effects between the laser current and temperature brought us to develop hybrid pre-equalizers to reduce the setting time and the transients [11].

The wavelength thermal stability and precision in DFB lasers is limited, depending on environmental conditions and ageing, being in the order of tenths of GHz in the long term and few GHz in the short term. On the other hand, the tolerable errors by the RX are about 1 GHz guard band at

Fig. 1: a) uDWDM PON; and b) Monitored DS & US optical spectrum at CO output.

locking-in, and about 50 MHz during operation [8].

For an efficient PON operation, the next features would be essential:

- The ONU setting-up process to be highly blind in order to cope with large uncertainties and drifts.
- Colorless in the sense that the ONUs are not preselected at the provisioning; and their wavelengths are unknown from the perspective of the OLT and the user.
- Non-intrusive, avoiding any collision crosstalk with the active connections in the PON.
- Highly transparent with respect to the data rate.
- Fast activation.

Considering these practical limitations and requirements, the coherent PON, as shown in Fig.1a, is proposed with a specific spectral organization (see example in Fig. 1b), as a feasible practical trade-off described below:

- The optical spectrum is divided in 100 GHz bandwidth segments, alternating downstream (DS) and upstream (US) every 50 GHz, with 8x 6.25 GHz channel slots. As each DFB/EML unit can be tuned into any of the 4 segments, and each segment can accommodate up to 8 channels downstream and 8 channels upstream, then 32 users can be accommodated in every group of 4 segments.
- Channels are placed consecutively in every segment from right to left, thus avoiding adjacent wavelength overlaps during activation [12].

- At the ONU, both the TX and LO light sources' are identical udWDM 10 GHz EML TO-Can units, which can be easily paired at a fixed wavelength spacing. Here they will be set at 50 GHz spacing by the own ONU, setting the US channel 50 GHz to the right of its corresponding DS channel. This is feasible in practice, since they are commonly tested and labelled at manufacturing. It has to be noted that the extinction ratio of the EML section is not high enough to block light emission, and overlap has to be avoided.
- Every segment has its own dedicated OLT-TX carrier located in the corresponding DS sub-segment, that is used as a reference carrier for the next ONU activation. At the initial connection, by signaling, the OLT-TX informs the new ONU to which segment has to jump, according to the general occupancy algorithm. The new OLT-LO will be available in the assigned slot, located in the corresponding US sub-segment, waiting for the new active ONU-TX.
- The OLT has an extra LO laser sweeping in coherent operation that acts as optical spectrum monitor of both DS and US, to continuously check the relative positions of each occupied channel working as a high resolution OSA. This functionality is the same that used by each ONU to detect the available OLT carrier.

Fig. 2: OLT and ONU lasers activation scheme.

III. NEW ONU ACTIVATION

For the allocation procedure of a new entrant ONU (here called ONU3) requesting connection the next steps are set, as illustrated in Fig. 2:

- a) The ONU-LO switches to high power bias being active at its manufactured wavelength into any US segment. Then it jumps 100 GHz left and waits for 2 seconds stabilization. The 100 GHz will take the ONU-LO into the left US band of the previous segment.
- b) The ONU-TX is set at same temperature than LO, but biased at low power near threshold to avoid disturbing other active ONUs. In this case it is 5 mA above threshold to guarantee an ONU-TX initial output power lower than 15 dB than the nominal power. This is required for 1dB penalty at RX, as we demonstrated in [13] where the BER was tested in a DPSK intradyne system as a function of the spectral separation between users for different signal-to-interference ratios. In consequence, the active ONU-TX appears deviated 30 GHz to the left of its paired ONU-LO.
- c) The ONU-LO scans from the previous 100 GHz up to find a reference OLT-TX into the closest DS segment, by sweeping the temperature. The ONU-RX detects the first OLT-TX anchor as a power maximum (its PSD in CW is higher than the existing modulated channels).
- d) It locks to it and reads the signalling pilot, enabling the communication [14]. If this segment is not available, a new target segment and slot number are assigned by the OLT, which sends this information to the incoming ONU. The steps e), f) & g) are required:
 - e) The ONU-LO jumps to that segment.
 - f) The ONU-TX jumps similarly, in low power state.
 - g) The ONU-LO scans the target segment and tunes finely to the target anchor.
- h) The ONU-TX powers up in the same 50 GHz DS segment,

thus avoiding overlaps at heating. The splitter strongly attenuates the Rayleigh-backscattering from the feeder fiber to ratios that do not penalize DS detection in the other operative ONUs as shown in [15].

- i) The ONU-TX is moved to the paired ONU-LO +50 GHz, to match the wavelength with the OLT-LO one.
- j) The OLT-LO finely locks the ONU-TX and, via the OLT-TX, informs the ONU about the precise position. It locks with the Automatic Frequency Controller (AFC) and it is finely positioned ready for bidirectional communication.
- k) Begins bidirectional data transmission, with continuous AFC and centralized spectral monitoring.
- l) The OLT sets a new available carrier, ready for the next ONU to connect.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental set-up uses seven DFB lasers in EML configuration for the activation procedure, as shown in Fig. 3a. A set of 3 optical sources are used as OLT TX/LO and another set of 2 light sources are used to model occupied DS channels by users in the second segment. These sources go to a splitter whose output passes through a 25 km SSMF, which models the PON. These signals go to the input of our ONU where a coupler mixes them with the ONU LO. The output of this coupler is photodetected and then, using a 180 MHz lowpass filter, a Schottky power detector measures the power of the electrical beating with our ONU-LO, which is read by an ADC connected to a computer. This LO scanning is equivalent to a tracking filter working as network inspector. The received signals are processed and control strategies are applied on both the ONU-LO and the ONU-TX through some DACs, implementing the described activation algorithm.

To monitorize the whole network in real time we combine all the optical signals with a coupler connected to an OSA, as shown in the figure. The coherent transceivers use direct modulation, as described in [8,13]. The TEC response time is a critical feature for the activation. Here, it is speeded up from 1.5 seconds to 300 ms using a control loop [11].

Fig. 3b shows the optical spectrum measured with the OSA at the beginning of the activation process. The initial OLT carrier reference to be found by the ONU-LO is at 1552.196 nm. There are two occupied DS channels 6.25 GHz and 12.5 GHz apart respectively. The new active ONU-LO powers up at 1552.828 nm. The ONU-TX, activated at low power, is 37.5 GHz to the left of its paired ONU-LO laser.

Following the steps shown in Fig.2, the ONU-LO will have to jump 100 GHz down to 1552.028 nm (Fig.2-label a) where it will start the scan searching for the OLT carrier Target 1 (Fig.2-label c). The OLT carrier for the ONU-LO to be finally matched for establishing the DS transmission is at 1553.9 nm (Target 2). The ONU-TX final allocation is 50 GHz to the right of its corresponding LO, where it will match to the available OLT-LO for US transmission (Target 3).

At the end of the activation process it must be guaranteed that the ONU-LO matches the OLT-TX Target 2 with a deviation lower than ± 1 GHz. This is the optimum tuning approach for the AFC lock-in circuit to take the wavelength

Fig. 3: a) Experimental Setup; and b) Network spectrum initial state

Fig. 4: Time evolution of ONU LO/TX: a) wavelength and b) power

control of the ONU-LO for the coherent data demodulation. Similarly, the ONU-TX must match the OLT-LO position with an accuracy better than ± 1 GHz.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 4a shows the evolution of the wavelength of the ONU LO and TX lasers along time, whereas Fig. 4b presents its power evolution. The steps of the proposed procedure are labelled in both pictures. Steps a) and b) are done simultaneously, lasting for less than 5 seconds including the 2 seconds of stabilization time required for minimizing the laser inertia before beginning the next step. In steps c) and d) the LO finds and locks to its nearest OLT carrier, and then reads the target segment and channel slot for its final allocation. The OLT algorithm determines that the current segment is fully occupied and not available for an incoming user. Consequently, the new ONU will be allocated in segment 4. Both steps together take around 10 s. In this case the scan time is about 4 seconds for scanning 25 GHz. The largest scanning time would be whenever the OLT carrier is at the right of its sub-segment (all channels available); in such case the ONU-LO must sweep the whole DS sub-segment, which would take from 8 up to 10 seconds. According to steps e) and f), the ONU lasers jump up to 180 GHz (this would be the largest case) simultaneously from Segment 2 to 4, in less than 5 s. The accumulated time up to here is 18 seconds. We observe a slightly power variation for the ONU-LO, whereas the ONU-TX is highly as laser temperature increases to reach the desired wavelength.

In step g) the ONU-LO scans 20 GHz and finds the target OLT carrier and locks to it in 4 s, taking the ONU-LO allocation about 20 s. Then in h) the ONU-TX is powered up instantaneously and it starts to operate at high power; the wavelength deviation due to power increasing results to be

within the safe DS sub-segment, being under the 50 GHz limit as observed, which guarantees no crosstalk between channels. This step takes less than 3 s, including the thermal laser stabilization time. In i) ONU-TX finds and finely locks to the target channel, with an accuracy of ± 400 MHz, below the 1 GHz tolerance, avoiding any overlap with the active channels. The total process lasts for about 25 seconds to reach the channel target precisely, without stressing the TEC and the laser currents, four times faster than for Butterfly packaging units [10].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated an activation protocol for udWDM coherent PONs, based in thermal tuning, with TO-Can EML units acting as wavelength agnostic ONUs, which guarantees fine allocation without wavelength overlap. The proposed system does not require additional hardware such as absolute wavelength reference and optical switch, as it consists only on a software blind control of the ONU laser modules and an allocation algorithm performed by the OLT.

The whole activation time resulted to be 25 seconds, being this the slowest case. The best case occurs whenever the ONU-LO appears within an available DS sub-segment, so steps e), g) and f) can be ignored, saving up to 9 seconds.

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